

THE EFFECT OF ORGANIZATIONAL CULTURE AND WORK DISCIPLINE ON THE PERFORMANCE OF HEALTH WORKERS AT MUSLIMAT MOTHER AND CHILD HOSPITAL, JOMBANG

Kusumaningdiah Sekar Jatiningrum¹, Ratna Wardani², Joko Prasetyo³

^{1,2,3}Master of Health Program, Graduate School, Strada Indonesia University

E-mail: kusumamieke@gmail.com¹

Received : 01 January 2026

Accepted : 10 February 2026

Revised : 15 January 2026

Published : 28 February 2026

Abstract

The performance of health workers reflects employees' work outcomes in terms of both quantity and quality. A decline in health workers' performance, or failure to meet hospital expectations, may negatively affect the quality of hospital services. Organizational culture adopted by an institution plays a crucial role in determining performance quality. In addition to organizational culture, work discipline is also a factor that influences performance. High work discipline is associated with improved performance. This study aimed to analyze the effect of organizational culture and work discipline on the performance of health workers at Muslimat Mother and Child Hospital, Jombang. This study employed a quantitative research design with a cross-sectional approach. The independent variables were organizational culture and work discipline, while the dependent variable was the performance of health workers. The population consisted of all health workers at Muslimat Mother and Child Hospital, Jombang, totaling 132 individuals. Using proportional random sampling, a sample of 100 respondents was obtained. Data were analyzed using logistic regression analysis. The results showed that organizational culture had a significant effect on the performance of health workers at Muslimat Mother and Child Hospital, Jombang ($p = 0.000$). Work discipline also had a significant effect on health workers' performance ($p = 0.000$). Furthermore, organizational culture demonstrated a statistically significant influence on health workers' performance ($p = 0.004$; OR = 0.023; 95% CI = 0.002–0.290), with a Nagelkerke's R Square value of 0.934. Organizational culture plays an important role in influencing the quality of health workers' performance, as it shapes values, norms, and collective behaviors, creates an environment that encourages collaboration, innovation, and work comfort, and indirectly enhances discipline and motivation, leading to improved performance.

Keywords: *organizational culture, work discipline, health workers' performance.*

INTRODUCTION

The presence of health workers is essential for hospitals, as it is one of the determining factors in achieving organizational goals. According to Susilowati (2020), the quality of health workers determines hospital success, not only in facing competition within the healthcare sector but also in maintaining commitment and consistency in improving health workers' performance. Yaslis (2014), as cited by Iqbal (2022), states that health workers' performance reflects employees' work outcomes in terms of both quantity and quality. A decline in performance or failure to meet hospital expectations may negatively affect the quality of hospital services. The study conducted by Agustin (2022) in inpatient wards at three hospitals found that 72 respondents (53.7%) demonstrated poor performance, while 62 respondents (46.3%) showed good performance.

Based on interviews with the Head of Human Resources for health workers, data from Muslimat Mother and Child Hospital, Jombang, in 2023 indicated that 6.17% of health workers demonstrated very good performance, 54.94% good performance, 29.63% moderate performance, and 9.26% poor performance. Meanwhile, employee attendance records revealed that many medical staff had not consistently recorded their arrival and departure times accurately. From January to March 2025, only 27% of health workers achieved 100% attendance compliance, indicating that approximately 63% could be categorized as having low attendance discipline. These findings indicate the need for efforts to improve health workers' performance. The persistence of suboptimal performance reflects a lack of employee awareness regarding the importance of work discipline, as well as insufficient enforcement of disciplinary sanctions by supervisors. Previous studies have shown that organizational culture is closely related to performance quality. Aprilianti and Syarifuddin (2022) found that organizational culture is a factor influencing

employee performance. Organizational culture adopted by an institution plays a critical role in determining whether performance outcomes are favorable or unfavorable. In addition to organizational culture, work discipline also affects performance; higher levels of discipline are associated with improved performance. The difference between the study by Aprilianti and Syarifuddin and the present study lies in the research subjects. While Aprilianti and Syarifuddin focused on employees of a public health office, this study examines health workers in a hospital setting. Their study concluded that organizational culture influences employee performance quality, whereas this study emphasizes the influence of organizational culture on health workers' performance through norms, beliefs, attitudes, behavioral patterns, and evaluation systems implemented at Muslimat Mother and Child Hospital, Jombang.

Organizational culture is a key determinant of organizational or hospital success. It represents a system of beliefs and attitudes established by the hospital. According to Sulastri (2017), organizational culture fosters a sense of belonging among health workers and guides work behavior. Darmin (2021) stated that to achieve effective and efficient health workers' performance for hospital advancement, organizational culture must be implemented as a work guideline that serves as a reference for daily activities. Thus, organizational culture plays a vital role in shaping health workers' performance. This is consistent with the findings of Harahap (2018), who reported a significant influence of organizational culture on health workers' performance. Work discipline is one of the indicators used to assess health workers' performance and serves as a communication tool between managers and subordinates to foster positive behavior, increase awareness, and ensure compliance with organizational rules and social norms (Hulwani et al., 2021). In this study, work discipline focuses on punctuality, effective use of working time, compliance with hospital regulations, achievement of work targets, and completion of daily work reports.

According to Juma et al. (2015), as cited by Vernadeth et al. (2021), work discipline ensures organizational order and smooth task implementation, resulting in optimal outcomes. For employees, good discipline creates a pleasant working environment and enhances work motivation. Effective discipline is reflected in employees' compliance with regulations, adherence to established work procedures, willingness to accept corrective feedback, observance of ethical codes, and compliance with institutional rules, all of which positively affect performance. Efforts to improve employee discipline may involve providing rewards or recognition for achieved performance, either in financial or non-financial forms. Although financial rewards remain dominant, non-financial rewards are equally important. Reward systems aim to enhance productivity, loyalty, and work discipline. Strong discipline reflects a high sense of responsibility toward assigned tasks. Expressions of appreciation from supervisors can serve as motivation for employees to perform their duties with discipline (Falaq, 2015, as cited in Hanifah et al., 2021). Based on the above discussion, it is evident that organizational culture and work discipline are critical factors in improving employee performance. Therefore, this study is entitled **"The Effect of Organizational Culture and Work Discipline on the Performance of Health Workers at Muslimat Mother and Child Hospital, Jombang."**

LITERATURE REVIEW

Health workers' performance is an important indicator for assessing the success of hospital services, as it reflects employees' work outcomes in terms of both quality and quantity. Optimal performance has a direct impact on service quality, patient safety, and public satisfaction. According to Mangkunegara (2017), performance is influenced by ability, motivation, and the work environment, while Nursalam (2017) emphasizes that health workers' performance is closely related to professional responsibility, teamwork, and compliance with service standards. Therefore, improving health workers' performance has become a strategic necessity for hospitals in addressing the increasingly complex challenges of healthcare service delivery.

Organizational culture is one of the main factors influencing health workers' performance. Organizational culture represents a system of shared values, norms, beliefs, and behavioral patterns within an organization that serve as guidelines for action (Robbins & Judge, 2018; Wirawan, 2016). A strong organizational culture fosters a sense of belonging, enhances organizational commitment, and encourages positive work behavior (Sulastri, 2017). Numerous studies have demonstrated that organizational culture has a significant effect on health workers' performance, where cultures that support collaboration, open communication, and professionalism contribute to higher motivation and improved service quality (Harahap, 2018; Darmin, 2021; Vernadeth et al., 2021).

In addition to organizational culture, work discipline plays an important role in improving health workers' performance. Work discipline reflects individuals' compliance with regulations, work standards, and responsibilities in carrying out their duties (Hasibuan, 2017; Sutrisno, 2017). Good discipline promotes punctuality, work efficiency, and consistency in implementing standard operating procedures, thereby positively affecting performance and service quality (Hulwani et al., 2021). Several studies indicate that work discipline is positively and significantly associated with health workers' performance, particularly in hospital service settings that demand high levels of

THE EFFECT OF ORGANIZATIONAL CULTURE AND WORK DISCIPLINE ON THE PERFORMANCE OF HEALTH WORKERS AT MUSLIMAT MOTHER AND CHILD HOSPITAL, JOMBANG

Kusumaningdiah Sekar Jatiningrum et al

accuracy, timeliness, and precision (Pratama & Juhaeti, 2023; Mailintina et al., 2024). Thus, the synergy between a strong organizational culture and good work discipline forms an essential foundation for sustainably improving health workers' performance.

METHOD

This study employed a quantitative approach with a cross-sectional design to analyze the effects of organizational culture and work discipline on health workers' performance. Data were collected simultaneously using a closed-ended questionnaire based on a Likert scale administered to 100 respondents selected through proportionate random sampling from a total population of 132 health workers at Muslimat Mother and Child Hospital, Jombang. The research instruments were tested for validity and reliability using SPSS software. Items were considered valid if the calculated correlation coefficient (r-count) was equal to or greater than the critical value (r-table), and reliable if the Cronbach's alpha value exceeded 0.60, indicating that the data were suitable for further analysis (Sugiyono, 2019; Hidayat, 2017; Ghozali, 2018).

The independent variables in this study were organizational culture and work discipline, while the dependent variable was health workers' performance. Organizational culture was measured using indicators of norms, beliefs, attitudes, behavioral patterns, and value systems. Work discipline was assessed based on punctuality, compliance with regulations, effective use of working time, and responsibility for assigned tasks. Health workers' performance was measured in terms of work quality and quantity, responsibility, cooperation, and initiative. All variables were categorized into good and poor categories using T-score values to ensure objective measurement (Wicaksono, 2021; Afandi, 2018; Mangkunegara, 2017). Data analysis involved several stages, including editing, coding, data entry, tabulation, and data cleaning prior to statistical analysis. Univariate analysis was used to describe respondent characteristics, while bivariate analysis employed the chi-square test to examine relationships between variables. The effects of independent variables on performance were analyzed using logistic regression, with model fit assessed through the Hosmer–Lemeshow test and the coefficient of determination (Nagelkerke R Square). This study also adhered to research ethics principles, including informed consent, anonymity, data confidentiality, fairness, and minimization of potential risks to respondents (Notoatmodjo, 2018; Swarjana, 2015; Ghozali, 2019).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This chapter presents the research findings obtained through univariate, bivariate, and multivariate analyses.

Description of the Research Site

Muslimat Mother and Child Hospital, Jombang, is a specialized hospital that provides 24-hour medical services. The hospital is strategically located in the city center at Jalan Urip Sumoharjo No. 34–36, Jombang 61417, East Java, Indonesia. The hospital can be contacted by telephone at +62 321 872200 and by email at rsiamuslimat_jbg@yahoo.co.id. Muslimat Mother and Child Hospital, Jombang, is a healthcare facility owned by the Muslimat Mother and Child Hospital Foundation. It is the only Type C specialized mother and child hospital in Jombang Regency and is currently led by Dr. H. Suparmin, Sp. OG, M. Si, as the Director. The hospital was officially established on November 16, 1969, as the Muslimat Maternal and Child Health Center (Balai Kesehatan Ibu dan Anak/BKIA) and later developed into Muslimat Mother and Child Hospital. The hospital achieved full (paripurna) accreditation in 2017. The hospital provides a wide range of medical services, including general outpatient clinics, obstetrics and gynecology specialist clinics, pediatric specialist clinics, pharmacy services, emergency care, and inpatient services. Inpatient facilities consist of Superior, VVIP, VIP, Class I, Class II, and Class III wards, supported by Radiology, Laboratory, PONEK (Comprehensive Emergency Obstetric and Neonatal Care), ICU, and NICU units equipped with advanced medical technology.

The vision of Muslimat Mother and Child Hospital, Jombang, is “*To become a Muslimat Mother and Child Hospital with excellent services inspired by Islamic values.*” Excellent service is defined as follows:

1. Services that exceed clients' needs and expectations.
2. Services that not only satisfy but also delight clients and foster loyalty.
3. Services that are accurate, fast, and affordable.
4. Standardized services based on the latest scientific evidence, supported by continuously standardized input, process, and output elements.

Islamic values are reflected in the acronym “KREATIF”, which represents:

1. Hard work in performing duties and providing services.
2. Courtesy and compassion in work and service delivery.
3. Effectiveness and efficiency in work and service provision.

THE EFFECT OF ORGANIZATIONAL CULTURE AND WORK DISCIPLINE ON THE PERFORMANCE OF HEALTH WORKERS AT MUSLIMAT MOTHER AND CHILD HOSPITAL, JOMBANG

Kusumaningdiah Sekar Jatiningrum et al

4. *Asih, asah, asuh* (care, guidance, and nurturing).
5. Accuracy, promptness, and caution in work and service.
6. Innovation.
7. Fact-based argumentation.

The missions of Muslimat Mother and Child Hospital, Jombang, are as follows:

1. To improve the competence of human resources through continuous education and training so that employees' skills and knowledge keep pace with scientific and technological developments, while fostering attitudes aligned with community culture based on Islamic values.
2. To provide comfortable facilities and standard-compliant equipment to support excellent services and create a pleasant working environment for all hospital employees.
3. To deliver high-quality medical and non-medical services that enhance customer satisfaction.

The hospital's motto is "*Your Satisfaction Is Our Trust: Healthy Mother, Healthy Child.*"

The goals of Muslimat Mother and Child Hospital, Jombang, include:

1. Ensuring the availability of highly competent human resources with integrity and strong organizational commitment through education and training initiatives, as well as the implementation of fair and humane welfare improvement programs.
2. Providing comfortable, pleasant, attractive, and aesthetically pleasing service facilities for both clients and employees.
3. Ensuring the availability of complete and standardized medical and non-medical equipment.

Characteristics of the Study Subjects

Table 1. Frequency Distribution of Gender, Profession, Highest Educational Attainment, and Length of Service

Characteristics	n	%
Gender		
Male	57	57
Female	43	43
Profession		
General practitioner	17	17
Perawat	44	44
Bidan	25	25
Medical laboratory analyst	5	5
Medical records officer	5	5
Pharmacist	4	4
Highest educational attainment		
Vocational (Diploma III, Diploma IV)	47	47
Professional (Bachelor's, Master's)	53	53
Length of service		
< 5 Years	47	47
> 5 Years	53	53

Source: Primary Data, 2025.

Based on the descriptive results presented in Table 1, the majority of respondents were male (57%), worked as nurses (44%), had a professional level of education (Bachelor's and Master's degrees) (53%), and had a length of service of more than five years (53%).

Validity Test

Validity is a measure that indicates the degree to which an instrument accurately and reliably measures what it is intended to measure. An instrument is considered valid if the calculated correlation coefficient (r -count) is greater than the critical value (r -table = 0.361) or if the p -value is less than the significance level ($\alpha = 0.05$). The validity test was conducted using responses from 30 respondents.

THE EFFECT OF ORGANIZATIONAL CULTURE AND WORK DISCIPLINE ON THE PERFORMANCE OF HEALTH WORKERS AT MUSLIMAT MOTHER AND CHILD HOSPITAL, JOMBANG

Kusumaningdiah Sekar Jatiningrum et al

Table 2. Results of the Validity Test for the Organizational Culture Questionnaire

No. Item	r Count	r _{table} 0,05 (5%)	p-value	α	Remark
1	0,511	0,361	0,004	0,05	Valid
2	0,923	0,361	0,000	0,05	Valid
3	0,568	0,361	0,001	0,05	Valid
4	0,923	0,361	0,000	0,05	Valid
No. Item	r _{hitung}	r _{tabel} 0,05 (5%)	p-value	α	Remark
5	0,697	0,361	0,000	0,05	Valid
6	0,723	0,361	0,000	0,05	Valid
7	0,733	0,361	0,000	0,05	Valid
8	0,704	0,361	0,000	0,05	Valid
9	0,779	0,361	0,000	0,05	Valid
10	0,410	0,361	0,024	0,05	Valid
11	0,603	0,361	0,000	0,05	Valid
12	0,733	0,361	0,000	0,05	Valid
13	0,694	0,361	0,000	0,05	Valid
14	0,511	0,361	0,004	0,05	Valid
15	0,923	0,361	0,000	0,05	Valid
16	0,568	0,361	0,001	0,05	Valid
17	0,923	0,361	0,000	0,05	Valid
18	0,697	0,361	0,000	0,05	Valid
19	0,723	0,361	0,000	0,05	Valid
20	0,733	0,361	0,000	0,05	Valid

Source: Processed by the authors

Based on the validity test, all 20 questionnaire items administered to 30 respondents were declared valid, as the calculated correlation coefficients (*r*-count) exceeded the critical value (*r*-table = 0.361) or the *p*-values were less than the significance level ($\alpha = 0.05$).

Table 3. Validity Test Results of the Work Discipline Questionnaire

No. Item	r Count	r _{table} 0,05 (5%)	p-value	α	Remark
1	0,686	0,361	0,000	0,05	Valid
2	0,636	0,361	0,000	0,05	Valid
3	0,543	0,361	0,002	0,05	Valid
4	0,745	0,361	0,000	0,05	Valid
5	0,745	0,361	0,000	0,05	Valid
6	0,543	0,361	0,002	0,05	Valid
7	0,543	0,361	0,002	0,05	Valid
8	0,543	0,361	0,002	0,05	Valid
9	0,543	0,361	0,002	0,05	Valid
10	0,543	0,361	0,002	0,05	Valid
11	0,745	0,361	0,000	0,05	Valid
12	0,745	0,361	0,000	0,05	Valid
13	0,543	0,361	0,002	0,05	Valid
14	0,543	0,361	0,002	0,05	Valid

Source: Processed by the authors

Based on the validity test results, all 14 items of the work discipline questionnaire were declared valid, as *r*-count > *r*-table (0.361) and $p < \alpha$ (0.05).

THE EFFECT OF ORGANIZATIONAL CULTURE AND WORK DISCIPLINE ON THE PERFORMANCE OF HEALTH WORKERS AT MUSLIMAT MOTHER AND CHILD HOSPITAL, JOMBANG

Kusumaningdiah Sekar Jatiningrum et al

Table 4. Validity Test Results of the Health Workers' Performance Questionnaire

No. Item	r Count	r _{table} 0,05 (5%)	p-value	α	Remark
1	0,763	0,631	0,000	0,05	Valid
2	0,970	0,631	0,000	0,05	Valid
3	0,928	0,631	0,000	0,05	Valid
4	0,928	0,631	0,000	0,05	Valid
5	0,729	0,631	0,000	0,05	Valid
6	0,970	0,631	0,000	0,05	Valid
7	0,970	0,631	0,000	0,05	Valid
8	0,928	0,631	0,000	0,05	Valid
9	0,970	0,631	0,000	0,05	Valid
10	0,970	0,631	0,000	0,05	Valid
11	0,763	0,631	0,000	0,05	Valid
12	0,970	0,631	0,000	0,05	Valid
13	0,970	0,631	0,000	0,05	Valid
14	0,928	0,631	0,000	0,05	Valid
15	0,970	0,631	0,000	0,05	Valid
16	0,928	0,631	0,000	0,05	Valid
17	0,928	0,631	0,000	0,05	Valid
18	0,970	0,631	0,000	0,05	Valid
19	0,928	0,631	0,000	0,05	Valid

Source: Processed by the authors.

Based on the validity test results, all 19 items of the health workers' performance questionnaire were declared valid, as $r\text{-count} > r\text{-table}$ and $p < \alpha$ (0.05).

Reliability Test

Table 5. Reliability Test Results of Organizational Culture, Work Discipline, and Health Workers' Performance Questionnaires

Questionnaire	Number of Items	Number of Respondents	Cronbach's Alpha	Minimum Alpha	Remark
Organizational culture	20	30	0,990	0,6	Reliabel
Work discipline	14	30	0,875	0,6	Reliabel
Health workers' performance	19	30	0,990	0,6	Reliabel

Source: Processed by the authors.

The reliability test results indicate that all questionnaires are reliable, as the Cronbach's alpha values for organizational culture (0.990), work discipline (0.875), and health workers' performance (0.990) exceed the minimum acceptable value of 0.60. Therefore, the instruments are considered appropriate for use in this study.

Normality Test

Table 6. Normality Test Results of Organizational Culture, Work Discipline, and Performance Variables

Variable	Kolmogorov-Smirnov ^a			Shapiro-Wilk		
	Statistic	df	Sig.	Statistic	df	Sig.
Organizational culture	0,082	100	0,094	0,976	100	0,065
Work discipline	0,072	100	0,200	0,975	100	0,058
Health workers' performance	0,082	100	0,090	0,981	100	0,155

Source: Processed by the authors.

THE EFFECT OF ORGANIZATIONAL CULTURE AND WORK DISCIPLINE ON THE PERFORMANCE OF HEALTH WORKERS AT MUSLIMAT MOTHER AND CHILD HOSPITAL, JOMBANG

Kusumaningdiah Sekar Jatiningrum et al

Based on Table 6, the significance values ($p > 0.05$) indicate that all variables are normally distributed.

Univariate Analysis

Table 7. Description of Research Variables

Variable	n	%
Organizational culture		
Poor	47	47
Good	53	53
Work discipline		
Poor	51	51
Good	49	49
Health workers' performance		
Poor	47	47
Good	53	53

Sumber : Data Primer, 2025.

Based on Table 7, more than half of respondents perceived organizational culture as good (53%), work discipline as poor (51%), and health workers' performance as good (53%).

Bivariate Analysis

Table 8. Chi-Square Test of the Effect of Organizational Culture and Work Discipline on Health Workers' Performance

Variable	Performance		OR	CI (95%)		p
	Poor	Good		Lower Bound	Upper Bound	
Organizational culture						
Poor	44(96,6%)	3(6,4%)	244.444	46.908	1273.823	<0.000
Good	3(5,7%)	50(94,3%)				
Work discipline						
Poor	47(92,2%)	4(7,8%)	13.250	5.164	33.997	<0.000
Good	0(0%)	49(100%)				

Source: Primary Data, 2025.

The bivariate analysis shows that good organizational culture is associated with good performance (94.3%), while poor organizational culture is associated with poor performance (96.6%). The odds ratio (OR = 244.444; $p < 0.000$; 95% CI = 46.908–1273.823) indicates a significant relationship between organizational culture and health workers' performance. Similarly, good work discipline was associated with good performance (100%), whereas poor discipline was associated with poor performance (92.2%). The odds ratio (OR = 13.250; $p < 0.000$; 95% CI = 5.164–33.997) indicates a positive and significant effect of work discipline on health workers' performance.

Multivariate Logistic Regression Analysis

Table 9. Logistic Regression Analysis of Organizational Culture, Work Discipline, and Health Workers' Performance.

Independent Variable	OR	CI (95%)		p
		Lower	Upper	
Organizational culture	0.023	0.002	0.290	<0.004
N Observations	= 100			
-2 log likelihood	= 17.909			
Nagelkerke R-Square	= 0.934			

Source: Primary Data, 2025.

The logistic regression analysis indicates a statistically significant association between organizational culture and health workers' performance (OR = 0.023; 95% CI = 0.002–0.290; $p < 0.004$). A poor organizational culture increases the likelihood of decreased health workers' performance, which may negatively affect service quality.

The Nagelkerke R Square value of 0.934 indicates that 93.4% of the variability in health workers' performance can be explained by the independent variables, while the remaining 6.6% is influenced by other factors not examined in this study.

Discussion

A. The Effect of Organizational Culture on Health Workers' Performance at Muslimat Mother and Child Hospital, Jombang

The study results indicate that a good organizational culture is associated with good health workers' performance (94.3%), whereas a poor organizational culture is associated with poor performance (96.6%). Hypothesis testing yielded a p -value of 0.000 (< 0.05), indicating a statistically significant effect of organizational culture on health workers' performance at Muslimat Mother and Child Hospital, Jombang. Organizational culture consists of organizational rules and shared values that serve as a foundation for improving employee performance to achieve organizational goals (Sulastri, 2017). Previous studies support these findings. Vernadeth (2021) reported that organizational culture significantly influences nurses' performance, where a stronger organizational culture leads to better performance, while a weaker culture results in performance decline. Similarly, Iqbal (2022) stated that organizational culture represents the identity of an organization and is closely related to the quality of nurses' performance. A decline in nurses' performance may negatively affect service delivery. Darmin (2021) also emphasized that effective organizations must establish a strong organizational culture within their work systems so that all staff, from management to frontline nurses, can achieve high performance. Organizational success is influenced by various factors, among which organizational culture plays a key role as an identity, guiding principle, unifying force, and behavioral regulator. From the researcher's perspective, organizational culture comprising norms, beliefs, attitudes, behavioral patterns, and core values has a positive influence on health workers' performance by enhancing motivation, collaboration, patient satisfaction, and service quality. Values such as innovation, empathy, teamwork, and open communication foster a supportive work environment. Conversely, a negative organizational culture may hinder performance. Therefore, healthcare management should focus on developing a supportive organizational culture through continuous training and strong leadership support to ensure optimal health workers' performance.

B. The Effect of Work Discipline on Health Workers' Performance at Muslimat Mother and Child Hospital, Jombang

The study findings show that good work discipline leads to good performance (100%), while poor discipline is associated with poor performance (92.2%). Hypothesis testing resulted in a p -value of 0.000 (< 0.05), indicating a statistically significant effect of work discipline on health workers' performance at Muslimat Mother and Child Hospital, Jombang. Work discipline plays an important role in organizations as it reflects an individual's sense of responsibility, encourages work enthusiasm, and increases awareness of organizational rules, thereby facilitating the achievement of organizational objectives (Siswanto, 2017; Hasibuan, 2017; Sutrisno, 2017). Pratama and Juhaeti (2023) found that work discipline is a crucial factor in improving employee performance across various dimensions, including productivity, efficiency, work quality, trust, and morale. The results of this study indicate that the highest discipline scores were associated with compliance in completing tasks according to established work regulations. This suggests that inpatient nursing staff strive to complete tasks in accordance with hospital rules, supported by leadership efforts to consistently remind employees to comply with internal regulations.

Furthermore, Rizal et al. (2024) reported a strong relationship between work discipline and employee performance, where higher discipline leads to improved performance. Similarly, Mailintina et al. (2024) found a positive correlation between work discipline and employee performance, indicating that increased discipline directly enhances performance. Their findings also highlight significant relationships among leadership role modeling, employee discipline, organizational responsibility, teamwork, and sense of belonging with employee performance. According to the researcher's interpretation, work discipline is closely related to health workers' performance because discipline encompasses adherence to rules, punctuality, and responsibility, which directly affect service quality, efficiency, and productivity in healthcare delivery. Disciplined health workers are more likely to comply with standard operating procedures, policies, and institutional regulations, thereby creating a safe and orderly work environment. Time discipline, such as punctual attendance, ensures timely service delivery, reduces patient waiting times, and enhances patient satisfaction, ultimately contributing to improved healthcare performance.

C. The Combined Effect of Organizational Culture and Work Discipline on Health Workers' Performance at Muslimat Mother and Child Hospital, Jombang

The logistic regression analysis revealed a statistically significant relationship between organizational culture and health workers' performance (OR = 0.023; 95% CI = 0.002–0.290; $p < 0.004$). A poor organizational culture increases the likelihood of decreased health workers' performance, which may negatively affect service quality. The Nagelkerke's R Square value of 0.934 indicates that 93.4% of the variability in health workers' performance can be explained by organizational culture, while the remaining 6.6% is attributable to other factors not examined in this study. These findings suggest that organizational culture plays a more dominant role in influencing health workers' performance at Muslimat Mother and Child Hospital, Jombang. According to the researcher's perspective, organizational culture shapes collective values, norms, and behaviors, creating a work environment that fosters collaboration, innovation, and comfort. This environment indirectly enhances discipline and motivation, leading to improved performance. In contrast, work discipline tends to be individual in nature and may be less effective if not supported by a strong organizational culture. Disciplinary sanctions alone are often insufficient to build long-term commitment and a positive work atmosphere without a solid cultural foundation.

This reciprocal relationship indicates that a strong organizational culture naturally supports work discipline, whereas a weak culture may undermine it. A culture that promotes discipline enhances performance more effectively than disciplinary enforcement without cultural support. In essence, organizational culture serves as the foundation of collective behavior and work atmosphere, while discipline represents individual behavior. A strong cultural foundation facilitates the enforcement of discipline and sustains long-term performance improvement in the healthcare sector. These interpretations align with the findings of Fardiansyah et al. (2025), who reported that a strong organizational culture encompassing shared values, norms, beliefs, and behaviors creates a conducive work environment, enhances motivation, and strengthens health workers' commitment. Similarly, Harun et al. (2025) found that strong organizational culture and work discipline contribute to a supportive work environment, increased motivation, and improved professional and efficient service delivery.

CONCLUSION

Based on the findings of this study, the following conclusions can be drawn:

1. Organizational culture has a significant effect on health workers' performance at Muslimat Mother and Child Hospital, Jombang ($p = 0.000$).
2. Work discipline has a significant effect on health workers' performance at Muslimat Mother and Child Hospital, Jombang ($p = 0.000$).
3. Organizational culture has a statistically significant and dominant effect on health workers' performance at Muslimat Mother and Child Hospital, Jombang ($p = 0.004$; OR = 0.023; 95% CI = 0.002–0.290), with a Nagelkerke's R Square value of 0.934.

REFERENCES

- Azwar. (2017). *Sikap Manusia, Teori dan Pengukurannya*. Yogyakarta: Pustaka Pelajar Offset.
- Afandi. (2018). *Manajemen Sumber Daya Manusia. (Teori, Konsep, dan Indikator)*. Riau : Zanafa Publishing.
- Aprilianti R dan Syarifuddin. (2022). Pengaruh Budaya Organisasi dan Disiplin Kerja Terhadap Kinerja Pegawai Pada Dinas Kesehatan Kota Bandung. *Jurnal Manajemen Sumber Daya Manusia, Adminstrasi dan Pelayanan Publik Universitas Bina Taruna Gorontalo Volume IX Nomor 2, 2022*.
- Agustin, Ismar. (2022). Analisis Sistem Penghargaan dan Beban Kerja Terhadap Kinerja Tenaga kesehatan Pelaksana Rumah Sakit Pada Masa Pandemi Covid-19. *Jurnal Ketenaga kesehatan Silampari Volume 5, Nomor 2, Juni 2022. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.31539/jks.v5i2.3289>*.
- Darmin. (2021). Hubungan Budaya Organisasi dengan Kinerja Tenaga kesehatan di RSUD Kota Amobagu. *Info Kesehatan. Vo. 11, No. 2, Juli 2021. 349-353*
- Bejo Siswanto (2017). *Manajemen Tenaga Kerja Indonesia : Pendekatan Administrasi dan Operasional*. Jakarta : Bumi Aksara.
- Edy, Sutrisno. (2017). *Manajemen Sumber Daya Manusia*. Jakarta : Kencana.
- Fardiansyah, et al (2025). Pengaruh Budaya Organisasi dan Disiplin Kerja Terhadap Kinerja Tenaga Kesehatan Pada Rumah Sakit Umum Daerah Kota Kendari. *Jurnal HOMANIS: Halu Oleo Manajemen dan Bisnis. Vol. 2, No. 2, Hal. 482- 497, April 2025*

THE EFFECT OF ORGANIZATIONAL CULTURE AND WORK DISCIPLINE ON THE PERFORMANCE OF HEALTH WORKERS AT MUSLIMAT MOTHER AND CHILD HOSPITAL, JOMBANG

Kusumaningdiah Sekar Jatiningrum et al

- Harun. FS, et al. (2025). Pengaruh Budaya Organisasi terhadap Kinerja dan Pelayanan Kesehatan di Puskesmas: Studi Tinjauan Literatur. *Jurnal Berita Kesehatan : Jurnal Kesehatan*, Vol. 18 No. 1 (Juni, 2025). Hal 122-130
- Harahap, Sridama Yanti. (2018). Pengaruh Budaya Organisasi dan Penerapan Standar Asuhan Ketenaga kesehatan Terhadap Kinerja Tenaga kesehatan di Ruang Rawat Inap RS. Martha Friska Brayana Medan. *Jurnal Darma Agung. Vol. XXVI, No. 1, Desember 2018. 677-685*
- Hasibuan. (2017). *Manajemen Sumber Daya Manusia*. Jakarta : Bumi Aksara.
- Iqbal. M. (2022). Faktor-faktor yang Mempengaruhi Kinerja Tenaga Kesehatan Aparatur Sipil Negara di Rumah Sakit Umum Daerah Kabupaten Lombok Utara. *Open Journal Systems. Vol. 16 No. 12 Juli 2022. 7901-7914*
- Mulyadi. (2015). *Manajemen Sumber Daya Manusia*. Bogor: In Media.
- Mangkunegara, Anwar Prabu. (2017). *Manajemen Sumber Daya Manusia*. Bandung : Remaja Rosdakarya.
- Manzilati. (2017). *Metode Penelitian Kualitatif, Metode Aplikasi*. UBPress.
- Moni Miftakhul Hanifah, Duwi Basuki, Raras Merbawani. (2021). Hubungan Disiplin Kerja dengan Kinerja Tenaga kesehatan Dalam Pelaksanaan Timbang Terima di RSUD Prof. Dr. Soekandar Mojokerto. *Jurnal Ketenaga kesehatan STIKes Bina Sehat PPNI Mojokerto*.
- Mailintina. Y, et al., (2024). Hubungan Disiplin Kerja Dan Loyalitas Kerja Terhadap Kinerja Pegawai Rekam Medis, Administrasi Ruang Rawat Inap dan Rawat Jalan di Rumah Sakit Umum Daerah (RSUD) Sawah Besar. *MAHESA: Malahayati Health Student Journal, Volume 4 Nomor 1 Tahun 2024. Hal 243-263*
- Nursalam. (2017). *Manajemen Ketenaga kesehatan: Aplikasi dalam Praktik Ketenaga kesehatan Profesional. Edisi 5*. Jakarta : Salemba Medika.
- Pratama. NA, dan Juhaeti, (2023). Pengaruh Budaya Organisasi dan Disiplin Kerja Terhadap kinerja Karyawan Bagian Keperawatan Rawat Inap di RS Yadika Kebayoran Lama Jakarta Selatan. *JIMEN Jurnal Inovatif Mahasiswa Manajemen VOL. 4, NO. 1 November 2023. Hal 51-63*
- Robbins, Stephan P. dan Timothy A. Judge. (2018). *Perilaku Organisasi. Organizational Behavior (Buku I, Edisi ke-12)*. Jakarta : Salemba Empat.
- Swarjana. (2016). *Metodologi Penelitian Kesehatan. (Edisi Revisi)*. Yogyakarta : ANDI
- Sulastris, Eritha. (2017). Pengaruh Budaya Organisasi, Motivasi, dan Kepuasan Kerja Terhadap Kinerja Karyawan PT. PLN (Persero) Wilayah Kalimantan Selatan dan Tengah Area Kuala Kapuas. *Jurnal Bisnis dan Pembangunan. Vol. 6, No. 2. Edisi Juli-Desember 2017. 129-138*.
- Silalahi. Ulber. (2017). *Asas-asas Manajemen*. Bandung : PT. Refika Aditama.
- Susilowati, Yuli. (2020). Pengaruh Kompetensi, Komunikasi, Budaya Organisasi, dan Pelatihan Terhadap Kinerja Tenaga kesehatan. *Dimensi, Vol. 9 No. 3, November 2022. 297-411*
- Thahrina Zatil Hulwani, Yusnika Damayanti, Kesaktian Manurung, Dina Andriani, Ithing. (2021). Hubungan Kompensasi dan Disiplin dengan Kinerja Tenaga kesehatan Unit Pelayanan Khusus di Rumah Sakit Umum Daerah Kota Langsa. *Jurnal Kesehatan dan Kebidanan STIKes Mitra RIA Husada. ISSN : 2252-9675 E-ISSN : 2722-368X VOL. X No. 2*
- Wirawan. (2016). *Budaya Organisasi Kepemimpinan dan Kinerja, Cetakan Kedua*. Jakarta : Kencana.
- Wibowo. (2018). *Manajemen Kinerja*. Jakarta : Rajawali Pers.
- Verly Vernadeth, Rina Anindita, Musaida. (2021). Pengaruh Budaya Organisasi terhadap Kinerja Tenaga kesehatan dengan Disiplin Kerja sebagai Variabel Intervening di RSUD Pesanggrahan. *Journal of Hospital Management. Vol.4, No.1, Maret 2021*
- Rizal. F, et al., (2024). Pengaruh Disiplin Kerja Dan Evaluasi Kerja Terhadap Kinerja Karyawan Pada Hotel Aston Batam Hotel & Residence. *Manajemen Kreatif Jurnal (MAKREJU). Vol. 2, No. 1 Februari 2024. Hal 62-77*